

TRENDS IN MODERN SCULPTURE

Usmanov Ulugbek Shavkatovich

Senior teacher of the Department "sculpture" at the National Institute of painting and design named after Kamoliddin Behzod
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7944515>

Annotation: In this article fully reflects on the directions of contemporary sculpture, elegant sculpture, monumental sculpture, monumental sculpture associated with architectural art, modern aspects of sculptural art in the territory of our country.

Keywords: modern sculpture, elegant sculpture, monumental sculpture, architectural art.

Introduction:

Sculpture is a form of fine art, derived from the Latin word "skulpo", meaning to process hard materials using "shearing, cutting, carving, combing". Sculptural processing methods, as well as details of a certain size in space, are depicted using shapes. There is also his type of "elegant sculpture". This method is called "Household plasticity" in sculpture.

Elegant sculptural items are distinguished by their elegance, small size. He can be captured and seen. In elegant sculpture, materials that quickly attract the attention of a person are widely used: porcelain, ceramic, wood, precious types of metals and stones, ivory and the like. One of the most common types of sculpture in school settings is work with clay or plasticine.

Literature analysis and methodology:

In fact, pencil painting is of particular importance in the study of sculpture. The next step in the study of art secrets also began to pay off. Of course, the study of Science and art depends on the mehru skills of the teachers. The 2 main manifestations of sculpture — a round sculpture that allows you to observe by rotation, as well as an embossed image, which is intended to be seen only on one side, differ in the type of relief. The relief, in due time, is divided into a slightly exaggerated bas-relief with respect to the surface, as well as a more exaggerated gorelyef than the image surface, and at the expense of the nursoya game there is a more carved look, in which the image is processed on a conspicuous flat surface.

In sculpture, the creator achieves an increase in the impact force of the work by using the play of nursoya. This is especially true for monumental and decorative sculptural works, the reason is that when the morning sunshine gives a charm to a statue placed on a square or alley, the sun's rays from the evening sunset introduce a different Grace. In sculpture, a person's opportunity does not end with the reflection of his appearance, quiet or moving state, while the work expresses experiences of experiences, excitement, sadness, etc.

Results:

Monumental sculpture, associated with architectural art, includes monuments, monuments, sculptural ensembles installed with the aim of perpetuating the memory of important historical events, outstanding personalities, which in themselves represent great content, as well as independent significance. However, this type of sculpture should be in

harmony with the immediate environment, architectural essay-horses and nature, which will give it even greater splendor and influence.

One of the qualities that is suitable for Monumental sculpture is the depiction of heroes in an uplifting spirit. Since Monumental sculptural works are intended to be seen from afar, large-large monolithic forms are widely used; small elements on a person's face, folds in clothing, small parts may not be displayed.

Decorative sculpture includes parks, alleys, streets and gardens, as well as various decorative sculptures that are used to decorate the walls of architectural buildings; in their works, symbolic images, The Shape of animals are widely used. Embossed images that are processed on the walls of buildings, ornaments that are processed on the surface of objects of Applied Art, fountains, fences, art gates are also manifestations of this sculpture.

Discussion:

The workshop sculpture works will look like a bust, torso, statue, figurine Colossus, genre sculpture and more. Small forms stand close to the art of practical decoration according to their character in the sculptor. This includes sculptures that are made of ceramic, porcelain and other raw materials that can be placed on the table. One of the most common types is terracotta; the art of medal making and glyptics are also characteristic of this type.

The skill of the sculptor, The correctly found movement, The Mimic position on the face occupy a special place in the impressive nature of the work. Various materials such as stone, granite, bronze, marble, wood, metal, cement, plaster are used for sculptural works. In sculpture, the selected raw material determines its color. There are cases of painting sculptures only in folk sculpture.

When creating sculptural works, soft substances are created by cutting from solids or removing unnecessary parts by carving; they are cast using a mold from substances that have the property of changing from a liquid state to a solid state; in the preparation of ceramic sculptural works, special clay varieties are used, the form is covered with a painting pattern or colored glaze and

In sculpting sessions, students get acquainted with the methods of rolling from clay or plasticine, pressing mint, tightening, removing excess parts with the help of a special diuretic, working with a stack. There are two different styles of work in sculpting exercises, which are performed using a holistic, separate treatment of clay or plasticine pieces.

Decorative sculpture is one of the types of sculpture, which generates special knowledge, as well as skills, through the work of various decorative decorative reliefs and toys in students. The simplicity of processing methods in decorative sculpture, the simplicity of your forms are of great interest to readers. The wide use of decorative sculptures of Uzbek folk Potters in the training of decorative sculpture has a high impact on the creative formation of children.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it can be said that Uzbekistan, along with its achievements in the economic-social sphere during its short years of independence, has increased its focus on ideological-spiritual, cultural work and has been raising its prestige and prestige among the developed countries of the world. The art of the fine bench of Uzbekistan developed at a very short time and achieved great success. Art of Uzbekistan took a triumphant path.

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